

Social Studies Students' Perception of and Attitude to E-Teaching During Covid-19 Lockdown at Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti

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Abstract:

This study examined social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during covid-19 lockdown at Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti. This study adopted descriptive research design of the survey type. The population of the study consisted of Social Studies undergraduates in Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti. The sample size was 140 Social Studies undergraduates purposely selected among 100 level to 400 level students. A self-designed questionnaire used was divided into three sections; section A sought for the demographics of the respondent such as gender, level and age, section B consisted of items on perception of E-teaching while section C consisted of items on attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. The face and content validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by experts of Tests and Measurement while test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability co-efficient value was 0.89. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher within a period of one week to the selected sample. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study that social studies students in Ekiti State University have high perception of and positive attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. The study also revealed that social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching were related. In addition, social studies students' perception of and positive attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown were not gender biased. It was recommended among others that University management should set up facilities that would influence the regular use of E-teaching by lecturers.

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Introduction

In December 2019, an outbreak of new coronavirus pneumonia emerged in Wuhan (Hubei, China) (Chen et al., 2020). In early 2020, coronavirus disease (COVID-19) began to spread, firstly throughout China, and then rapidly throughout the world, with Europe in general and some countries in particular like Spain becoming strongly affected by contagion and deaths caused by the pandemic. This rapid and unprecedented pandemic has created significant mental health problems such as stress, anxiety and, depression for both medical professionals and the general population alike (Liu, et al., 2020).

Since the pandemic started till date (2nd October, 2021), globally about 235,334,498 people have contracted the virus, out of which 212,090,031 million recovered while 4,809,890 deaths were recorded (Wikipedia, 2021). In Africa, over 8 million cases were recorded while in Nigeria, 205,940 cases were recorded, 193,812 discharges have been made while 2,724 deaths were documented for the virus (Wikipedia, 2021), yet the figure is still counting, the world is not yet freed from its hold. It kept disrupting global activities relating to economic, educational etc., as nearly all countries of the world have temporarily closed their institutions as a measure in curbing the spread of the pandemic (De Giorgio, 2020).

A new variant of the virus emerged in South Africa, which had migrated to about 40 countries the variants could not easily be tracked because the type of testing required to identify them isn't available yet in most countries. Experts believed its emergence led to the upsurge in number of both cases and deaths recorded (Mwal, 2021).

From inception to now, the attainment of educational objectives in the Nigerian University system has been achieved through non electronic teaching and learning methodologies. Dobbs et al. (2017) posited that the traditional educational system required having students on campus and taking lectures, examinations, seminars and other academic assignments in classrooms in physical buildings. The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic has necessitated the adoption of E-teaching by Universities across the world. E-teaching form of learning is done in real-time with an instructor facilitating live discussions and lectures with students in the learning process. Students 'attending' class can, in fact, be situated anywhere in the world. Participants log in at a set time and interact directly with the instructor and with the other class participants (Lei & Gupta, 2010). This form of learning is facilitated by electronic media that are capable of engaging people in different locations at the same time. E-teaching provides greater flexibility of access and is essentially a web-based system that makes information or knowledge available to students and disregards time limitations or geographic proximity (Nakamura, 2018).

Dobbs et al. (2017) stated that students' attitude refers to students' impression of participating in E-teaching activities through computer usage. Therefore, E-teaching depends largely on the utilisation of computers as a supporting tool. Consideration of students' attitude is an integral part of E-teaching, as attitudes influence not only students' initial acceptance of IT but also their future behaviour regarding computers (Kurt & Yildirim, 2018). Kurt and Yildirim (2018) revealed that various research has indicated that students' attitude towards information technology is an important factor in e-learning fulfilment. Students from different education and cultural backgrounds may have different perceptions towards higher education particularly expectations related to E-teaching and E-learning. Thus, this study investigated social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during covid-19 lockdown at Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti. This study specifically:

1. examined the social studies students' perception of E-teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;

2. described the social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;
3. assessed the relationship between social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during COVID-19 lockdown;
4. examined gender differences in social studies students' perception of E-teaching during COVID-19 lockdown; and
5. determined gender difference in social studies students' attitude towards E-teaching during COVID-19 lockdown at Ekiti State University.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

1. What is the social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?
2. What is the social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Research Hypotheses

These hypotheses were postulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.
2. There is no significant gender difference in social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.
3. There is no significant gender difference in social studies students' attitude towards E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design of the survey type. The population of the study consisted of Social Studies undergraduates in Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti. The sample size was 140 Social Studies undergraduates purposely selected among 100 level – 400 level students.

A self-designed questionnaire used was divided into three sections; section A sought for the demographics of the respondent such as gender, level and age, section B consisted of items on perception of E-teaching while section C consisted of items on attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. The face and content validity of the questionnaire was ascertained by experts of Tests and Measurement while test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability co-efficient value was 0.89. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher within a period of one week to the selected sample. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Table 1: Social Studies Students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

	Items	N	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	I feel confident during E-teaching.	140	3.11	0.54	Accepted
2.	I enjoy E-teaching.	140	2.79	0.51	Accepted
3.	I am satisfied with learning online content.	140	3.28	0.62	Accepted
4.	I enjoy multimedia instructions available during E-teaching	140	3.09	0.57	Accepted
5.	I believe content of E-teaching is informative.	140	3.16	0.58	Accepted
6.	I believe E-teaching is a useful learning tool.	140	3.40	0.49	Accepted

7.	Learning contents provided during E-teaching are useful.	140	3.18	0.60	Accepted
8.	E-teaching is assisting my learning.	140	3.07	0.61	Accepted
	Total	140	25.08	2.17	
	Average		3.14		Accepted

Mean Cut-Off: 2.50

Table 1 shows the social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. Based on the mean cut-off, all the items were accepted which implies that they have high perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Research Question 2: What is the social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown?

Table 2: Social studies students' attitude towards E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown

	Item	N	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	I prefer E-teaching to conventional teaching.	140	2.78	0.61	Accepted
2.	Finding my way around E-teaching class is more convenient than the conventional class.	140	2.99	0.64	Accepted
3.	It is easy to understand E-teaching without getting acquainted with appropriate guidance	140	2.94	0.63	Accepted
4.	It am always eager to learn through E-teaching	140	2.64	0.59	Accepted
5.	Note taking during E-teaching is not tasking	140	2.21	0.52	Rejected
6.	Learning through E-teaching is very convenient	140	2.60	0.60	Accepted
7.	Unstable internet connections discouraged me during E-teaching	140	2.47	0.54	Rejected
	Total	140	18.63	2.41	
	Average		2.66		Accepted

Mean Cut-Off: 2.50

Table 2 shows the social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. Based on the mean cut-off as the average mean value of 2.66 is greater than 2.50, it is concluded that social studies students have positive attitude to E-teaching.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 3: Relationship between social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching

		Perception	Attitude
Perception	Pearson Correlation	1	.703
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	140	140
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.703	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	140	365

*P<0.05

The results presented in Table 3 revealed a significant relationship ($r = .703$; $p = .000 < .05$). This shows that social studies students' perception of E-teaching has high and positive relationship with their attitude to E-teaching. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there was significant relationship between social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant gender difference in social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 4: Independent t-test to show gender difference in social studies students' perception of E-teaching

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	T	P value
Male	58	24.97	2.89	138	0.972	.431
Female	82	25.23	2.32			

*P<0.05

Table 4 showed that there is no significant gender difference in social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown as $t_{(138)} = 0.972$, $p = .431$. Based on this, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there was no significant gender difference in social studies students' perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant gender difference in social studies students' attitude towards E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Table 5: Independent t-test to show gender difference in social studies students' attitude towards E-teaching

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	T	P value
Male	58	18.67	2.10	138	0.203	.818
Female	82	18.61	2.18			

*P<0.05

Table 5 showed that there is no significant gender difference in social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown as $t_{(138)} = 0.203$, $p = .818$. Based on this, the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there was no significant gender difference in social studies students' attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that social studies students have high perception of E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. It is in line with the result of the study conducted by Mustafa (2015) who stated that students do not feel bored when they learn through E-teaching. Using E-teaching tools can develop students' learning experience since they increased the level of students' engagement in improving students' educational outcomes

(Alahmari, 2017). The platform also breaks their learning routine and it motivate them to interact and share information between peers. Working with computer will make students learn more quickly, show greater retention, and are better motivated to learn (Kurt & Yildirim, 2018). The use of technology can gain students' interest because it satisfies their technology addiction. The digital-native students can be interested in learning because they like the fact that they utilize technology in the classroom (Mustafa, 2015).

The study also revealed that social studies students have positive attitude to E-teaching. It has been proved that a positive attitude is created when students are not afraid to engage with ICT tools. It was found that the use of new technologies contributed to the development of a positive attitude for students. This is in tandem with the findings of Ashong and Commander (2012) which found that there was an important impact on the students' attitudes toward E-teaching.

It was further revealed that social studies students' perception of E-teaching has high and positive relationship with their attitude to E-teaching. This implies that the interest level and engagement with new technologies by undergraduates may help explain the favourable perception the participants had toward E-teaching, which equally reflected in their attitude. This finding is in consonance with the study of Costa, Faria and Neto (2018) who found that relationship existed between students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching.

The findings of the study however revealed that there was no significant gender difference in social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. The probable reason for this finding could be because being a male or female has nothing to do with E-teaching. This is corroborated with the findings of Peck, et al., (2018) who found that gender of the students has no influence on students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching.

Conclusion

The study concludes that social studies students in Ekiti State University have high perception of and positive attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown. The study also concludes that social studies students' perception of and attitude to E-teaching were related. In addition, social studies students' perception of and positive attitude to E-teaching during Covid-19 lockdown were not gender biased.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are considered plausible and necessary in order to improve our nation educationally and economically.

1. University management should set up facilities that would influence the regular use of E-teaching by lecturers.
2. The use of blended learning which accommodates but E-teaching and conventional classroom should be included in the mode of teaching of undergraduates by National University Commission.
3. Lecturers' knowledge of information and communication technology should be updated by university management.
4. Free internet services should be provided for students within the university environment while subsidized internet fee should be granted to undergraduates who are not within the school environment.

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